

Job Stress on Teachers During the Covid-19 Pandemic: The Role of Workload and Organizational Climate

Tri Na'imah¹, Syarif Akbar Nur²

¹A lecturer in Faculty of Psychology, Universitas Muhammadiyah Purwokerto, Indonesia

²A Student in Faculty of Psychology, Universitas Muhammadiyah Purwokerto, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: The number of workloads borne by the teacher will result a negative impact. An organizational climate is crucial because it can generate a comfortable working conditions for teachers. Otherwise, an unfavorable organizational climate can impact poor working conditions that affect teachers to experience job stress. This study aimed to determine the effect of workload and organizational climate on the work stress of elementary school teachers in Indonesia. One hundred forty-eight elementary school teachers were selected as research participants through an incidental sampling. The research instruments were the workload scale, organizational climate scale, and teacher job stress scale. The results of regression analysis revealed that workload ($\beta = 0.134$, $p = 0.026$) and organizational climate ($\beta = -0.680$, $p = 0.000$) contributed to the job stress of elementary school teachers. This study recommends primary school principals to manage the workload for the professionalism improvement and productivity of elementary school teachers. Harmony in the school environment must be maintained to create a comfortable work and avoid work stress.

KEYWORDS:- Job Stress, Workload, Organizational Climate, Teacher, Elementary School

I. INTRODUCTION

Schools are a crucial component of education and training systems in each country and play an essential role for both improvement and development of an educational system (Ahghar, 2008). Primary school teachers occupy a crucial position in providing early education. Improving the quality of primary school teachers is very important to prioritize in forming qualified human resources. The teachers are required to play active roles in efforts to fulfill the goals of primary education. Therefore, they must learn various kinds of functions, such as the roles as teacher, model, advisor, authority holder, reformer, guide, executor of routine tasks, visionary person, realistic person, storyteller, researcher, and assessor (Pullias & Young, 1968).

Various teacher roles require teachers to improve other supporting abilities, namely skills to operate gadgets and master the internet, communication skills, and others (Fahmi et al., 2019). Teachers in Indonesia also have to bear a high workload including administrative tasks, to design teaching materials, lesson plans, material analysis, and to prepare semester or annual programs (Sanaky, 2013). Moreover during the current pandemic, school activities which were initially carried out face-to-face turned to online learning carried out from their respective homes. Many teachers face difficulties and are burdened with online learning because they have not been able to operate online learning platforms. Weak ability to optimize technology or online learning applications, lack of direct communication with students, poor internet signal are obstacles experienced by teachers during online learning (Baalwi, 2020).

Various stressors in the school environment and conditions must also be faced by teachers (Chan, 2010). These sources come from job demands, including time pressure, lack of administrative support, low student motivation, discipline problems, value conflicts, diverse student characters, conflicts among the teachers, and role ambiguity (Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2018). Other various teacher problems, such as interpersonal demands, lack of appreciation, lots of work to be completed, disciplinary issues in the classroom, bureaucracy, time constraints, correction jobs for student evaluation results, excessive workload, and lack of support, will make teachers feel depressed (Kokkinos, 2007). They also have to deal with achieving student scores when carrying out exams and school reputation problems that must be maintained (Cui et al., 2018).

Considering the lots of tasks, roles, and responsibilities that must be borne by the teacher, of course, will result negative impact. Excess workload and demands, role conflict/ambiguity, and poor working conditions will make teachers prone to stress (Nafs, 2020). Stress is an imbalance between the heavy burden faced and the ability to cope with the commitment (Sundberg et al., 2002). Job stress is a feeling of pressure experienced by teachers in dealing with a job (Fimian & Fastenau, 1990). Teacher is one of the professions with a lot of pressure that causes job stress (Ravichandran & Rajendran, 2007). The high workload and great responsibility are things that the teacher must bear. The excessive workload can affect a person's physical and psychological

Job Stress on Teachers During the Covid-19 Pandemic: The Role of Workload and Organizational Climate

condition (Dhanias, 2010), including fatigue at work (Woranetipo & Chavanovanich, 2021). The huge workload, role ambiguity, poor working conditions, inadequate environment, and facilities are the root causes of teacher stress. It is influenced by several factors, namely individual factors, organizational factors, and environmental factors (Robbins & Judge, 2007), such as role ambiguity and workload (Keenan & Newton, 1984). Organizational factors that can have an impact on job stress are organizational climate. A closed and unhealthy organizational climate creates negative feelings for teachers and students; it also creates dissatisfaction, psychological pressure, neglect, indifference, and work stress (Ahghar, 2008). Organizational climate impacts one's behavior and attitudes, such as work motivation, productivity, and satisfaction (Adenike, 2011). In other words, an excellent organizational climate can increase motivation and work productivity. On the other hand, an unfavorable organizational climate can reduce motivation and work productivity which is a sign of experiencing job stress. In line with this, the research results show that a healthy organizational climate will directly impact low job stress (Ahghar, 2008).

There are three symptoms of job stress, namely psychological, physiological and behavioral symptoms. Psychological symptoms include anxiety, irritability, sensitivity, withdrawal, feeling isolated, bored, dissatisfied with performance, decreased concentration, mental fatigue, reduced creativity, decreased intellectual function, and low self-confidence. The physiological symptoms include increased blood pressure, tend to experience cardiovascular disorders, physical tiredness, dizziness, pain in some regions of the body, sleep disturbances, and decreased body immunity. The behavioral symptoms cover procrastination, reduced productivity, irregular eating, and decreased interpersonal relationships with family and friends (Asih et al., 2018). These conditions will reduce the quality of services and impact family workers (married teachers) and others even though they must be responsible for student learning activities through learning interactions.

Research on work stress is needed to be carried out further to avoid the adverse effects of work stress experienced by teachers. In addition, workload and organizational climate are essential things to consider in their contribution to work stress. Therefore, this study focuses on these three variables. The correlation between workload, organizational climate, and work stress has been widely studied in several hospital settings, industry, field workers, and various professions such as nurses, company employees, and the police. Still, this study focuses on elementary school settings and elementary school teachers' jobs in Indonesia. This study aimed to examine workload and organizational climate on teachers' work stress in Indonesia.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Several previous studies have proven that work stress is influenced by several variables such as hardiness (Prasetyo et al., 2018), self-resilience (Akbar & Prataswi, 2017), forgiveness (Setiyana, 2013), and leadership style (Prayatna & Subudi, 2016). Researchers are interested in workload and organizational climate variables to strengthen previous research proving that workload affects work stress (Conard & Matthews, 2008). Kokoroko & Sandi (2019) examined nurses, hotel employees (Diane & Tremblay, 2016), junior high school teachers (Wahdaniyah & Miftahudin, 2018), pharmaceutical marketing employees (Dhanias, 2010), and tahfidz teachers (Nafs, 2020). Organizational climate has also been shown to affect work stress on salesmen (Nasurdin et al., 2006), school teachers (Ahghar, 2008), and police (Angelina & Ratnaningsih, 2016). The framework of thought developed by the researcher is as follows:

A. Workload and Job Stress

Stress is an imbalance between the heavy burden and the ability to cope with the responsibility (Sundberg et al., 2002). Work stress results from an individual's response to external or internal factors that impact psychological and physical tension, thereby reducing employees' ability (Cooper & Payne, 1994). Stress is a response to adjusting to a situation, mediated by psychological processes caused by demanding external activities and events. (Gibson et al., 2006). Every individual can experience stress in any environment and conditions, including work environment and conditions. Ten dimensions of job stress are time management, work-related stress, career investment, behavioral manifestations, emotional manifestations, gastronomic manifestations, cardiovascular manifestations, fatigue manifestations, work difficulties, discipline, and motivation (Fimian & Fastenau, 1990).

During this pandemic, school activities have been changed to technology-based online learning. But in reality, there are still many teachers who do not understand the application of learning technology. This condition increases the workload of teachers in carrying out their professional duties (Baalwi, 2020)

The workload is an imbalance between the ability of workers and the demands of the work. The workload can be physical or mental (Hart & Staveland, 1988). It is a set of job demands, effort, and activity or achievement (Gawron, 2008). The workload is a work task that must be carried out according to predetermined criteria and plans and requires concentration and time pressure (Nurendra, 2016). It impacts the psychological and physical health of employees (Dhanias, 2010). Excess workload and demands, role conflicts, and poor working conditions will make teachers experience stress (Nafs, 2020). Therefore, the first hypothesis is:

H1: Workload affects teacher job stress

B. Organizational Climate and Job Stress

Organizational climate is the quality of the organization's internal environment that is long enough and continues to be experienced by organization members. It affects behavior and can be described as a reflection to an organization's values and

Job Stress on Teachers During the Covid-19 Pandemic: The Role of Workload and Organizational Climate

characteristics (Tagiuri & Litwin, 1968). Organizational climate is the atmosphere of the work environment in the organization. It is measured based on employees' views so that it affects motivation, ability, and competitive advantage (Brown & Leigh, 1996). Organizational climate is a relatively enduring quality experienced by employees influences their behavior and is based on their collective perceptions (Madhukar & Sharma, 2017). The organizational climate was produced from organizational context (e.g., purpose, size, resources, technology) and structure (hierarchy, authority system, structuring of role activities) (Borman et al., 2003). There are nine dimensions of organizational climate: structure, responsibility, reward, risk, warmth, support, standards, conflict, and identity (Litwin & Stringer, in Setiawan, 2015). Conversely, an unfavorable organizational climate can impact a decrease in work productivity which is a sign of someone experiencing job stress.

A stressful organizational climate is characterized by limited decision-making participation. Employees are not informed about policies, work activities are limited to routines, use of punishment and negative feedback, no group support, poor relationship with leaders, physical facilities work environment is not managed well. Herefore, a comfortable organizational climate can cause employees to be free from stress and improve the quality of work (Singh & Dhawan, 2012). The second hypothesis in this study is:

H2: Organizational climate affects teacher job stress

III. METHOD

The participants were 148 elementary school teachers in Indonesia, consisting of 44 male teachers and 104 female teachers. The participant selection technique used incidental sampling. The age of the participants ranged from 22-60 years, with 1-40 years of working experience.

The research instrument applied a Likert scale consisting of a teacher's job stress scale, workload scale, and organizational climate scale. The teacher's job stress scale is based on ten aspects time management, work-related stress, career investment, behavioral manifestations, emotional manifestations, gastronomic manifestations, cardiovascular manifestations, fatigue manifestations, work difficulties, discipline, and motivation (Fimian & Fastenau, 1990) with the total of 49 items ($\alpha = 0.965$). The workload scale was based on six aspects: physical demands, effort, mental demands, demands related to time, frustration level, performance (Rubio et al., 2004) with a total of 20 items ($\alpha = 0.853$). The organizational climate scale was based on nine aspects; structure, responsibility, reward, risk, warmth, support, standards, conflict, and identity (Litwin & Stringer, in Tagiuri & Litwin, 1968), with a total of 51 items ($\alpha = 0.973$). All research instruments were modified into the Indonesian version and adapted to the conditions of primary school teachers as participants

This study employed a correlational research design. Before collecting data, the researchers applied for a research permit to the Head of the Education Office. Furthermore, data collection was implemented by distributing respondents a set of research instruments and giving them time to study and fill it out. Data collection took place April – May 2021. The data analysis technique used in this research was linear regression analysis.

IV. RESULT

The participants of this study were 148 elementary school teachers in Indonesia. Description of participant characteristics is presented in table 1:

Table 1. Demographic Data

Criteria	N	%
Gender		
Male	44	29,73
Female	104	70,27
Age		
22– 30 years old	27	18,2
31– 40 years old	47	31,8
41– 50 years old	25	16,9
51– 60 years old	49	33,1
Working Experience		
< 1 years	5	3,4
1 – 10 years	48	32,4
11 – 20 years	52	35,1
21 – 30 years	17	11,5
31 – 40 years	26	17,6

Job Stress on Teachers During the Covid-19 Pandemic: The Role of Workload and Organizational Climate

The average value and standard deviation are presented in table 2. The average of each variable is higher than the actual average score of the instrument, so the importance of job stress, workload, and organizational climate are in the high category.

Table 2. Data Description

Variable	N	Minimum Score	Maximum Score	Mean	Standard Deviation
Job Stress	148	52	173	112,57	19,28
Workload	148	55	86	70,20	6,03
Organizational Climate	148	138	252	202,39	20,13

Description of the data in this study used empirical data and based on the table above, it can be concluded that the value of N or the number of samples in this study were 148 respondents, the minimum value or the lowest or smallest value among all members in the data group in the work stress variable was 52, in the workload variable is 55, and in the organizational climate variable is 138, for the maximum value or the highest value or the most significant value among all members in the data group on the work stress variable is 173, in the workload variable is 86 and in the organizational climate variable is 252. The mean or average value in this research data group for the work stress variable is 112.57; for the workload variable, it is 70.20, and the organizational climate variable is 202.39, while for the SD value (standard deviation/standard deviation), the work stress variable is 19.28, the workload variable is 6.03 and organizational climate variable of 20.13. The Standard Deviation Value is a statistical value used to determine how the data is distributed in the sample and how close the data points are to the average of the sample values.

The regression test results for the effect of workload on job stress obtained an F value = 4.390 and the probability value of sig. (p) = 0.038 (p < 0.05), so it can be declared as significant, and t = 2.095 and the probability value is sig. (p) = 0.038 (p < 0.05), so it can be stated as significant. The regression test results for the influence of organizational climate on work stress obtained the calculated F value = 130.644 and the probability value of sig. (p) = 0.000 (p < 0.05) so that it can be significant, and t = -11.430, and the probability value is sig. (p) = 0.000 (p < 0.05), so it can be said to be significant. So the first hypothesis and second hypothesis are proven empirically in this study.

Table 3 presents the coefficient values of each predictor:

Table 3. Coefficient Value for Job Stress

	B	t	p
Organizational Climate	-0.680	-11.447	0.000
Workload	0.134	2.250	0.026

V. DISCUSSION

The results of this study examine the issue of elementary school teacher problems in Indonesia. The results of data analysis prove that the work stress of elementary school teachers is determined by the workload and the school's organizational climate. This finding strengthens the results of previous studies, which stated that there was a significant positive effect of workload variables on work stress (Kokoroko & Sanda, 2019; Nafs, 2020). The excessive workload can affect a person's physical and mental condition (Dhania, 2010), increasing stress at work (Robbins & Judge, 2007).

Excessive workload, role conflict, poor working conditions, inadequate environment, and facilities are the root causes of teacher stress. Some problems are also faced by teachers, namely interpersonal demands, lack of appreciation, various types of work to be completed, disciplinary issues in class, bureaucracy, time constraints, many student assignments that must be corrected, excessive workload, and lack of support, thus making teachers feel depressed at work (Kokkinos, 2007). This study proves that a person's workload affects the emergence of work stress.

This study proved that a person's workload contributed to or influenced the emergence of work stress. This reflected that the higher the workload, the higher the work stress experienced. In addition, a bad organizational climate also increases teacher work stress (Ahghar, 2008). A healthy organizational climate will directly impact lower work stress (Abdillah et al., 2016) because the emergence of stress is influenced by environmental factors, organizational factors, and individual factors (Robbins & Judge, 2007). A possible organizational factor affecting work stress is the organizational climate because it can create a conducive work environment (Angelina & Ratnaningsih, 2016).

Maintaining an excellent organizational climate is very important because it can make workers feel comfortable, experience friendly, and achieve full work abilities as the key to competitive advantage (Brown & Leigh, 1996). The organizational climate will impact a person's behavior and attitudes, such as work motivation, productivity, and job satisfaction (Adenike, 2011). A conducive organizational climate can increase work productivity. Otherwise, a non-conducive corporate environment can reduce

Job Stress on Teachers During the Covid-19 Pandemic: The Role of Workload and Organizational Climate

work productivity, a sign of someone experiencing work stress. This condition meant that the more conducive the work organization climate, the more reduced teacher work stress.

Stressors could come from the work environment, working conditions, organization, career, position, human relations, family, and individual, including personality, attitude towards work, length of employment, education, and past experiences (Kiov & Kohn, in Kusnadi, 2014). The workload was an external factor in the emergence of work stress from the work environment and working conditions.

Excessive workload, role conflict/ambiguity, poor working conditions, inadequate environment, and facilities are the root causes of teacher stress (Keenan & Newton, 1984). Teachers who are given an extra burden in carrying out their work will be at risk of experiencing psychological problems, including the emergence of work stress (Nafs, 2020). The emergence of stress is influenced by environmental, organizational, and individual factors (Robbins & Judge, 2007), including workload and organizational climate. Pressure is when the load experienced is too heavy and not balanced with the ability to cope with the burden experienced (Sundberg et al., 2002). Stress is a response to adjustment to circumstances, mediated by psychological processes (Gibson et al., 2006). Demands, roles, work assignments, poor working conditions, inadequate environment, and facilities cause pressure on teachers. The type of workload experienced by teachers can provide a separate burden for each teacher, both in terms of mental, social, and physical, and the ever-changing organizational climate so that it becomes a challenge for schools to create a calm, safe, and comfortable atmosphere.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study illustrates empirical evidence that a low workload will have a direct impact on low work stress. A healthy organizational climate will have an immediate effect on low work stress. Teachers must experience an intense workload and a healthy organizational climate to reduce job stress, increase work productivity, and maintain teacher professionalism.

This study has a limitation because it only applies independent variables in the form of teacher external factors. Further researchers need to have more attention to internal factors unavailable in this study, such as self-regulation, hardiness, self-efficacy, self-control, emotional intelligence, and other internal factors.

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Job Stress on Teachers During the Covid-19 Pandemic: The Role of Workload and Organizational Climate

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